

PRESERVING MOTHER NATURE IS OUR SACRED DUTY

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Abstract: this article provides general information about the preservation of mother nature.

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Every inch of land in our country is worth gold. Its beautiful nature, clean air, crystal clear and healing waters will fascinate anyone. It is the duty of each of us to preserve this unique beauty and pass it on to future generations.

June 5 - International Environment Day is widely celebrated around the world every year. This date was introduced by the United Nations General Assembly at the 1972 Stockholm Conference on the Human Environment.

Over the years, this day has been celebrated in more than 100 countries, and now it serves as an important platform for solving environmental problems. In addition, on this day, all nations will have the opportunity to unite and make their personal contribution to the protection of the environment and the preservation of our motherland.

Nature itself is like a jeweler. Every plant, every tree, forest, animal world that sprouted from his bosom is a world of its own. Prevention and protection of this natural wealth is not only the work of the employees of this field, but everyone's duty. Because the cleanliness and ecological balance of the area we live in are equally important to all of us. In short, let's be kind to mother nature. Let's strengthen environmental education in families, neighborhoods and villages. It is necessary to observe mediocrity, to take care of the place of flowers and trees. If we make a habit of not harming natural beauty, we will be more concerned about the future of generations and the continuity of life. According to information, every hour the species of animals and plants on our planet is decreasing by one. Therefore, the world community celebrates May 22 as International Biodiversity Day every year in order to prevent such problems. Indeed, today the preservation of nature on our mother planet has become a global problem. Efforts to solve this issue are reflected in our national legislation.

During the years of independence, great attention has been paid to preserving the uniqueness of nature, expanding the area of forests and preserving unique plant and animal species, and reducing the negative impact on nature. Consequently, the 1995 International Convention on Biodiversity Conservation was ratified in our country. Also, specific legal bases for protection of biological resources were created. In addition, a national biodiversity conservation strategy and action plan has been developed and is being consistently implemented. As a result of such efforts, it was possible to save rare creatures and plant species.

Natural reproduction of gazelle, kulon, and Przewalsky horses was achieved at the "Jayron" eco-center belonging to the State Committee for Nature Protection of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Also, more than two hundred species belonging to 28 plant families are being bred in this center.

Scientific researches related to the world of animals and plants are consistently conducted at the center. For example, the biological, physiological and ecological characteristics of animals and plants were studied, and manuals and programs were created. The good thing is that the scientific research on the study of the gazelle, which is being reproduced in natural conditions, is the only one in the world practice. For this reason, the Russian Research Institute of Nature Studies, the French National Center for Nature Studies, the International Wildlife Conservation Fund and other leading scientific centers abroad are working in cooperation with our scientists.

Scientific and practical projects in this direction are being implemented in a number of other regions of our country. A program aimed at studying and preserving endangered plants and mammals is being implemented in the Hisar State Reserve. In the Peshku district, two nurseries specializing in the reproduction of the quilted canvas included in the "Red Book" have been launched. Regular monitoring is carried out in the Aydar-Arnasoy lake system in order to protect rare fish species. Problems related to the preservation of fish species there are being solved.

It is known that planting trees and creating a garden has been formed as an immortal value of our people. Pay attention, how many trees are over a hundred years old in our country?! It's fun for many people. So far, nine hundred trees of such a magnificent age have been registered by local governments and given the status of "natural monument".

It is no exaggeration to say that the "Central Asian Interstate Project on the Conservation of the Biodiversity of the Farbiy Tien-Shan Mountains"

implemented on the basis of a grant of the Global Environmental Fund was one of the most important works in this regard. Within the framework of the project, work was carried out for four years and the negative impact on the environment was reduced. This project, which was implemented in cooperation with the scientific institutions of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan, the Ministry of Agriculture and Water Management, the State Committee for Nature Protection and a number of international organizations, is specialized not only in preserving biological diversity, but also in preserving the genetic characteristics of plants. was very important. In recent years, as a result of various projects implemented in our country, animal and plant species in need of human support were identified and registered. Now, based on this list, a new edition of the "Red Book" of the Republic of Uzbekistan will be created. Also, the creation of a new cadastre of the fauna and flora of our country is being actively continued. Work in this regard has been completed in Jizzakh, Navoi regions and the Republic of Karakalpakstan.

Our people have been showing special love for nature since time immemorial. It is not a secret to anyone that in recent years attention has been paid to this matter at the state level, and it has become the main factor in solving the issue quickly and efficiently. Nature is the eternal source of human life. After all, what is the pleasure of protecting nature and living in its more beautiful bosom?

Man has always lived in harmony with nature. A child who grows up enjoying nature tries to understand existence. If we think about it, the things, equipment, and clothes we need are actually the priceless products of our mother nature. Great attention is being paid to beautification of our motherland. The main goal is serunum, to make our rich soil bloom more and use it productively. For this reason, the streets of the cities are planted with colorful flowers that are pleasing to the eye.

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